

AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION LEVEL OF VARIOUS TAX SAVING INVESTMENT INSTRUMENTS OF SALARIED PEOPLE

Shilpa S Research Scholar, Department of Commerce Sree Saraswathi Thyagaraja College,
Thippambatti, Pollachi

Dr.Kothaiandal C Associate Professor, Department of Commerce Sree Saraswathi Thyagaraja
College, Thippambatti, Pollachi

ABSTRACT

Tax planning is the most crucial financial strategy that every taxpayer should develop. This strategy is the most effective and efficient while following the provisions of income tax legislation to reduce the tax burden. At present, both the state as well as central governments are facing numerous problems such as an increase in tax compliance, changing tax slabs, introduction of new regimes, and complicated procedures in return filing. As a result, tax planning has become a high priority. So, every individual taxpayer should make better tax planning. Hence, this paper focused on studying awareness and perception levels of various tax-saving investment instruments. This study is conducted in Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu, and the sample for the study includes the salaried employees through the structured questionnaire the data has been collected. A stratified sample method was adopted to collect data from 50 respondents. Statistical tools such as ANOVA, Chi-square, mean, and percentage analysis were used to analyze the data. The result highlighted certain factors like gender, nature of the family, annual income, awareness about various investment instruments, perception towards taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act, and satisfaction level on their investments.

Keywords: Income Tax, Tax Planning, Tax avoidance, investment instruments, salaried employees

INTRODUCTION

India is an emerging nation. Tax is a significant factor for the government which helps to develop its fiscal policies; India's government needs money to become a developed nation. Tax collection is one of the main ways to raise money. Taxes are also imposed by the government to ensure income equality throughout the nation. The more money a person makes, the more tax he must pay. India has a sophisticated tax system with a clear division of power between the Central, State, and municipal governments. In India, there are two types of taxes: direct taxes and indirect taxes (Goyal, 2008). Tax is the government's main source, raising revenue to spend on public services. It is compulsory to all the assesses which are charged on goods, income, and any other service activities. As per the Constitution of India, it is binding on the Government to levy taxes on persons. The Central Board of Direct Taxes, which is a part of the Department of Revenue under the Ministry of Finance of the Indian government, is vested with the power of collection of taxes The CBDT functions as per the Central Board of Revenue Act of 1963. In the last 1015 years, the Indian taxation system has undergone remarkable reforms. The tax laws have been simplified and the tax rates have been rationalized resulting in better compliance, ease of tax payment, and better enforcement. (Pallavi 2018)

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Income tax is levied on all earnings of the individual based on the taxable income slab. It is a compulsory contribution to the Govt and is charged annually, there are many tax deductions, and exemptions that all individuals can claim to reduce the tax liability. It is a major problem that gather all necessary documents for tax purposes, a single missing document can lead to huge trouble while paying the tax so, it's a good strategy to keep all invoices, statements, and documents for the next tax season. A little prudence in the beginning can support long-term. Still, many investors struggle to manage their tax planning strategies effectively, which makes it difficult to comply with tax laws and increase their returns. Despite the availability of different tax preparation tools, the investors typically lack adequate knowledge and skills to manage the complicated tax system, resulting in various concerns such as high tax rates and available investment opportunities in the field. It is very important

to gain knowledge to develop and implement effective tax planning strategies while investing in various tax-saving investment instruments available under income tax law. Hence, this study supports to gain knowledge on various tax saving investment instruments.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study included the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the level of awareness of the salaried employees on various tax-planning instruments.
2. To measure the level of perception of tax-saving investment instruments.

Significance of the study

Financial planning is very important to secure the future, in meanwhile the Income Tax Department also prescribed numerous tax measures to reduce the tax burden through annual budgets, and circulars to avail the benefits for salaried employees. However, many of them are still struggling to understand the concepts and procedures. So, this study attempted to bring together several tax plans measures available to salaried employees and educate them about the remaining measures.

Scope of the study

There are numerous investment avenues and investment instruments which very complicated to understand during tax planning. The scope of this study is limited to the tax planning instruments adopted by the salaried income tax assesses of the Coimbatore district. The study also evaluates the extent of awareness of employees on investment avenues and instruments. The saving habits, investment patterns, investment schemes, and tax planning measures adopted for the period under the study and the level of awareness and impact of employees on tax planning measures were studied and evaluated.

HYPOTHESIS

1. **H₀**: There is no significant association between gender and their awareness of various tax planning instruments.

H₁: There is a significant difference between employment nature and their awareness of various tax planning instruments.

2. **H₀**: There is no significant variance among the income of a family of the respondents and their level of perception.

H₁: There is significant variance among the income of a family of the respondents and their level of perception

METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The primary data was collected from 50 salaried employees of the Coimbatore district through a structured questionnaire using Google Forms.

Source of Data

- Using the survey method primary data has been collected from the respondents by administering the Google digital form and evaluating the feedback.
- Secondary data included information collected from various Internet downloads, official websites, books, publications, and journals.

SAMPLING DESIGN

Population

- The population for the study is mainly ITR-filing salaried people of the Coimbatore district.

Sample size

- The sample size for the study is 50 respondents.

Sampling Technique

- Stratified Sampling Technique is used for this study.

Analysis of Data:

The data has been analyzed with different statistical tools like Chi-square, ANOVA, correlation, etc., through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for this study.

Limitations of the study

- Most of the respondents are busy so they are not willing to spend much time providing information.
- As the sample size is too small, the results may not be accurate.
- Some respondents may be reluctant to answer tax-related questions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Anuradha & Anju** (2015) attempted to recognize the investor's behavior concerned with income, saving, and investment. The researcher identified that IT professionals can increase their wealth with proper investment strategies and financial planning which contribute to standard economic growth and increase the quality of life even though the financial service sector offers different investment avenues. It was concluded that this research is most applicable to investors to plan their proper wealth management and to policymakers, investment agencies, managers as well and researchers.
2. **Siti and Saidatulakmal** (2017) carried out research to assess the taxpayers concerned with income tax payments and income tax returns. The stratified random sampling techniques were used and 30 academic and administration staff were taken as samples in UiTM, Kedah. The author assumed that specific knowledge on tax compliance influences tax compliance behavior which could result in accurate tax returns and positive consequences that lead to the right tax computation among the taxpayers, thus keeping in mind the conclusion that tax payer's knowledge and good understanding level of deciding what should be declared while computation even though when laws and policies keep on changes such as classification, deductions, tax relief, and tax rates.
3. **Mariyah and Atik** (2021) surveyed to find out the financial planning and tax saving in the region of Pune. They have taken 190 samples and used a non-probability sampling technique to analyze the saving pattern and found savings could be increased when they prefer medical plans, pension plans, and plans. They have suggested that cutting down unnecessary expenses could lead to better savings for the future, keeping 10-15% of earnings as savings each month reduces the burden of uncertainty. In addition, a few recommendations were given for successful investments such as starting at the earliest, regular investment and saving, making use of tax shelter, and regularly monitoring investment plans.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Gender and Awareness level of different investment instruments (T-Test)

S.No.	Particulars	Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	SI
1	Public Provident Fund	Male Female	38 12	4.08 3.50	1.024 1.382	t= 1.567 df= 48 0.124>0.05 Not Significant
2	ELSS Tax Saving mutual funds	Male Female	38 12	3.63 2.92	1.125 900	t= 2.003 df=48 0.051>0.05 Not Significant
3	Tax saving bank fixed deposit schemes	Male Female	38 12	3.76 3.83	1.051 0.835	t= -211 df=48 0.834>0.05 Not Significant
4	Senior citizen saving schemes	Male Female	38 12	3.32 3.92	1.068 0.996	t= -1.725 df=48 0.091>0.05 Not Significant
5	Voluntary provident fund	Male Female	38 12	3.32 3.33	1.254 1.231	t= -0.042 df=48 0.966>0.05 Not Significant
6	New pension scheme	Male Female	38 12	3.53 3.83	1.202 1.030	t= -0.796 df=48 0.430>0.05 Not Significant
7	National saving certificate	Male Female	38 12	3.29 3.50	1.271 1.446	t= -0.484 df=48 0.631>0.05 Not Significant
8	Unit-linked investment (insurance) plan	Male Female	38 12	3.58 4.17	1.244 0.937	t=-1.503 df=48 0.139>0.05 Not Significant
9	Sukanya Samriddhi account	Male Female	38 12	3.76 4.42	1.283 0.793	t= -1.661 df=48 0.103>0.05 Not Significant

Source: Primary Data

Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the overall level of awareness about investment instruments.

H0: There is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the overall level of awareness about investment instruments.

Interpretation

It is inferred from the table that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and their level of awareness on investment instruments such as PPF, ELSS, tax saving bank deposit, senior citizen saving schemes, VPF, NPS, NSC, Unit linked investments plan and Sukanya Samriddhi account.

However, there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and overall awareness about investment instruments.

It is observed from the statistical analysis that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the overall level of awareness about investment instruments. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Pearson Chi-Square Test

Particulars	Pearson Square Value	Chi-df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Public Provident Fund	2.170 ^a	3	.538
ELSS –Tax saving mutual funds	5.330 ^a	4	.255
Tax saving bank fixed deposit schemes	3.682 ^a	4	.451
Senior citizen saving schemes	9.029 ^a	4	.060
Voluntary Provident Fund	9.559 ^a	4	.049
New Pension Scheme	10.290 ^a	4	.036
National Saving Certificate	5.576 ^a	4	.233
Unit Linked Investment (insurance) Plan	3.816 ^a	4	.431
Sukanya Samriddhi Account	9.434 ^a	4	.051

Hypothesis2

H1: There is a significant association between the nature of the family of the respondents and the overall level of awareness about tax planning instruments.

H0: There is no significant association between the nature of the family of the respondents and the overall level of awareness about tax planning instruments.

Interpretation:

It inferred from the table that there is a significant association between the nature of family of the respondents and the various dimensions of the awareness about tax saving instruments such as voluntary provident fund, new pension scheme, and Sukanya samriddhi account.

However, there is no significant association between the nature of family of respondents and their awareness about tax planning instruments such as public provident fund, ELSS, tax saving bank deposit schemes, senior citizen saving schemes, and national saving certificate ULIP. It is also observed from the statistical analysis that there is a significant association between the nature of family respondents and the overall awareness of tax-saving investment instruments.

It is observed from the statistical analysis that there is a significant association between the nature of family of respondents and the overall level of awareness about tax-saving investment instruments. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The annual income of respondents and perception towards taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act.

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ANOVA Table

Particulars		Sum Squares	of df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Income tax rates are high	Between Groups	2.995	2	1.498	1.508	.232
	Within Groups	46.685	47	.993		
Understanding of tax system in India is highly complicated	Between Groups	1.205	2	.602	.669	.517
	Within Groups	42.315	47	.900		
Withdrawal of Standard Deduction has adversely affected me	Between Groups	3.076	2	1.538	2.083	.136
	Within Groups	34.704	47	.738		
Tax exemption limit is not sufficient	Between Groups	6.626	2	3.313	4.331	.019
	Within Groups	35.954	47	.765		
Surcharge should be avoided	Between Groups	7.315	2	3.658	3.531	.037
	Within Groups	48.685	47	1.036		
Deduction for bank interest should be reinforced	Between Groups	1.742	2	.871	.958	.391
	Within Groups	42.738	47	.909		
The maximum limit for Deductions u/s 80C should be increased	Between Groups	3.815	2	1.907	2.647	.081
	Within Groups	33.865	47	.721		
Filing of return is very complex	Between Groups	.185	2	.092	.095	.910
	Within Groups	45.815	47	.975		
score of awareness of tax planning instruments	Between Groups	8.292	2	4.146	.087	.917
	Within Groups	2251.488	47	47.904		

Hypothesis:

H1: There is significant variance among the annual income of respondents and their perception towards taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act.

H0: There is no significant variance among the annual income of respondents and their perception of taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act.

Interpretation

It is inferred from the table that there is a significant variance among the annual income of the respondents and their perception towards taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act such as tax exemption is limited and not sufficient and surcharges should be avoided.

However, there is no significant variance among the annual income of the respondent and their perception towards taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act such as Income tax rates are high, understanding of the tax system in India is highly complicated, 'withdrawal of standard deduction has adversely affected me', 'deduction for bank interest should be reinforced', 'the maximum limit for deductions u/s 80C should be increased', and 'filing of return is very complex' hence null hypothesis is accepted.

The satisfaction level of the respondents

Are you satisfied with your investments?

Interpretation:

The above diagram shows that only 8.3% of the respondents are very much satisfied, 79.2% of respondents are satisfied and the remaining 12.5% of the respondents are not satisfied with their investments.

Findings

- Majority of the respondents (72%) are male.
- Majority of the respondents are married.
- There is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the overall level of awareness about investment instruments.
- There is a significant association between the nature of family respondents and the overall level of awareness about tax-saving investment instruments.
- There is no significant variance among the annual income of the respondent and the perception towards taxation procedures under the Income Tax Act.
- Majority of the respondents (79.2%) are satisfied with their investments.

Suggestions

- It is necessary for the assesses to gain subject knowledge of both the Income Tax Act and the annual budget.
- As per study majority of the female respondents invested very less amount so they should come forward to invest more in the tax saving instruments.
- It would be appreciable if the tax-paying mechanism was convenient and simplified.
- More advertisements like detailed brochures should be provided by the financial institutions to improve the awareness level of the respondents.

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- The government and tax authorities are suggested to conduct more awareness programs among the salaried people.

Conclusion

Sources from tax are help to overall national development so it's very much necessary to invest for the future and pay tax for the financial year to reduce tax burden based on the savings of the individual. Tax is given high priority in every country, each small contribution makes a huge difference which helps to develop the nation hence invest more, and save for future in the mean while paying taxes to the government. This study focused on salaried people, in which many of the respondents were not aware of the various tax planning investment instruments so it's required to gain more knowledge on tax planning to get complete benefit. It would suggest that the government and tax authorities conduct more tax plan awareness programs among salaried people.

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